

D3.2

Mapping tool box to assess land management impact

Date: 27.01.2025

Version: 1.2

**Funded by
the European Union**

SOIL O-LIVE (Grant Agreement ID: 101091255) is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EIC. Neither the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Document Information

Project title	SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES
Project acronym	SOIL O-LIVE
Grant Agreement	101091255
Work package	WP3 - Soil erosion and land degradation
Deliverable number and title	D3.2 Mapping tool box to assess land management impact
Deliverable description	Modelling and mapping toolbox suitable for stakeholders to assess the influence of land management on soil erosion
Deliverable type	OTHER
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Lead beneficiary	UNIROMA3
Due submission date	31 December 2024 (M24)
Submission date	28.04.25

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Document history

Version	Date	Made by	Short Description of Changes
1.1	15.01.25	Borrelli P. Kaffas K. Matthews F. Saggau P. Alewell C.	UNIROMA3, UNI BASEL
1.2	27.01.25	Borrelli P. Alewell C.	UNIROMA3, UNI BASEL

Datasets associated with the deliverable

1. LPIS-based dataset of olive groves across EU: <https://zenodo.org/records/14748127>
2. Soil O-live dashboard: https://borrellilab.shinyapps.io/olive_dashboard/

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

CORINE	CORINE Land Cover (CLC)
EU	European Union
GIS	Geographic information system
LPIS/GSA	Land Parcel Identification System / GeoSpatial Aid Application
LUCAS	Land use and land cover survey
UNIROMA3	Università degli Studi Roma Tre

Executive Summary

Sustainable land management in agriculture is essential for balancing ecological, economic, and social goals. The Soil O-live project developed the Soil O-live Dashboard, an interactive web tool assessing land management impacts on soil degradation in European olive groves. Integrating geospatial datasets, satellite imagery, and field data, it supports data-driven decision-making for stakeholders.

Built using the shiny package in R, the Dashboard provides interactive maps, statistical tools, and data visualizations. By improving the spatial definition of olive groves using LPIS/GSA data from EU Member States, it offers higher accuracy than CORINE Land Cover data. A subset of 10,405 olive parcels was selected along with the 53 52 Soil O-live pilot sites, ensuring integration of spatial and survey data (including LUCAS).

The current version of the Dashboard offers insights into 40 environmental variables. Users can visualize datasets, perform statistical analyses, and explore soil health factors. Future developments will expand its capabilities, including further data gathered or generated by the project activities. By advancing geospatial analysis, we believe that the Soil O-live will contribute to improved land management policies in Europe.

Introduction

Sustainable land management in agricultural production is essential for balancing ecological, economic, and social goals that lie at the heart of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (Silander, 2020). However, while new data and knowledge is generated on a daily basis, the assessment of the impacts of diverse land management practices requires new tools that can integrate diverse information and provide actionable insights. This project report presents the web toolbox which was developed as part of the Soil O-live project's WP3 research activity to capture spatial patterns on a variety of environmental and anthropogenically derived factors in olive groves across Europe. A web toolbox that will expand in tandem with the Soil O-live project's achievements, and, ultimately, by the end of the project will help disseminate insights into the effects of land management on soil degradation across Europe.

The web toolbox, named Soil O-live Dashboard, represents a collection of geospatial datasets that have been pre-processed and analysed in GIS environment and then integrated with the shiny package (Chang et al., 2025) within the R environment to create an interactive and user friendly Dashboard for uploading, downloading, and visualizing spatio-temporal data. By integrating GIS data, satellite imagery, field data, and advanced algorithms, the O-live Dashboard facilitates data-driven insights assisting the decision-making of the project and beyond. Furthermore, it provides stakeholders such as land managers, politicians, and academics with a scalable framework for visualizing spatial patterns, measured variables as well as generated composite products.

This report outlines the development of the Soil O-live Dashboard, describes some of its key functionality, and highlights some functionalities demonstrating its application in the Soil O-live project contexts. While the Soil O-live Dashboard's current version 1.0, as detailed in this report, is already available online, the full range of functions and data results achieved by the project will be available in future dashboard updates.

2 Material and Methods

2.1 Spatial definition of olive groves in Europe

Prior to the work of the Soil O-live WP3, the CORINE Land Cover (Büttner et al., 2000) was the only source of information on the spatial distribution of olive groves at pan-European level. Olive groves are represented in class 223 of the CORINE products, which identify regions with olive occupancy of more than 50%. Here, available georeferenced agricultural parcels data in EU Member States was gathered from the national LPIS/GSAA (Montanarella and Wojda, 2023) collections to develop an improved pan-European dataset that more accurately depicts the distribution of olive groves in Europe compared to CORINE products. LPIS/GSAA comprises georeferenced parcels, which compared to the pixels in the CORINE product, enable a more accurate definition of specific olive groves as target areas and the extraction of harmonized information. This allows for object-oriented image analysis during GIS and remote sensing operations. As a result, georeferenced parcels related to olive groves were collected from all relevant nations' LPIS/GSAA collections (Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Slovenia, and Spain), and a dataset available for download online was developed (<https://zenodo.org/records/14748127>). The data refers to the years 2021, 2022 and 2023 and is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: An overview of the LPIS/GSA available for download on Zenodo.

Country	Data type	No. of parcels	Area (km ²)	year	Data source
Croatia	GSA	69,471	173.6	2022	APPRRR
France	GSA	19,425	135.7	2022	IGN
Greece	GSA	1,074,512	3,531.6	2023	Opekepe
Italy	LPIS	1,073,198	8,340.3	2022	Agea
Portugal	GSA	401,561	3,088.4	2021	IFAP
Slovenia	GSA	3,287	8.5	2022	RKG
Spain	GSA	3,738,409	26,494.2	2022	FEGA
Total		6,379,863	41,772.3		

2.2 Statistical design of monitoring networks

To select a statistically significant subset of the more than 6.3 million LPIS/GSA parcels collected, we used the same standards as the Land Use/Cover Area Frame Survey (LUCAS) (Belin et al., 2018), which provides harmonised and comparable statistics on land use and land cover across the entire EU territory. Through an overlay analysis, we selected all the LPIS/GSA parcels in our dataset that spatially coincided (overlay) with a point of the LUCAS master sample (Eurostat [link](#)), a 4 Km² (2x2 km) with 1,033,759 points covering the EU-27 territory. This sampling design creates a synergy between the spatial information in LPIS/GSA and the information components and survey structure of the multiple LUCAS survey modules (land cover, topsoil, grassland, Copernicus, and photos), maximising the ground-truth information which is available for large scale assessments.

2.3 Building the Shiny App mapping toolbox

The shiny app (<https://shiny.posit.co/>) (Chang et al., 2025) is used for creating interactive web applications, enabling dynamic data visualization and real-time analysis. The core strength of shiny lies in its reactive programming model (R and Python), where changes in user inputs automatically update outputs without requiring manual refresh. This capability supports exploratory data analysis, hypothesis testing, and interactive simulations, making it an invaluable tool for researchers and analysts. In addition, shiny applications are well-suited for complex visualizations, geospatial mapping, showcasing statistical insights, and multi-faceted dashboards, facilitating the presentation of high-dimensional data.

Shiny, with its capacity to assure accessibility and scalability, as well as handle real-time user interactions, represents an ideal choice for creating a data-driven dashboard developed to help decision-making and improve the reproducibility of scientific findings via interactive tools. In the case of our Soil O-live Dashboard, besides the online interface, the source script and data will be made available for the soil community. The online dashboard contains visual framework composed of an interactive map displayer, table viewers, data tables, descriptive statistics, and some dynamic graphics.

2.4 Identification of the suitable input variables

Table 2 shows the list of the 40 environmental variables extracted so far from each LPIS/GSA parcels as well as the 52 Soil O-live pilot sites. The variables currently separate into four different variable types: topography, climate, land use/cover and soil, giving a holistic overview of environmental and management related conditions across the sample of olive groves.

Variable types are further distinguishable by their temporal characteristics, depending on if they vary spatially or both spatially and temporally. For example, land use/cover variables are represented via statistical aggregations (e.g. the average and standard deviation) of their temporal properties over a one-year period. Climatic variables, by definition, represent a 30-year period, accounting for the long-term variability of each variable type across space. Soil and topographic variables are considered as temporally static, therefore only their spatial variability is considered. All variables are spatially aggregated per LPIS/GSA parcel based on relevant statistical metrics for each variable, such as the mean, median, minimum, maximum and standard deviation.

Table 2: List of environmental variables pre-processed and included in the online O-live Dashboard v1.0.

Category	Variable
Topographical	Altitude
	Slope
	Aspect
	LS factor
	Gravelius Index
Climate	Precipitation
	Air temperature
	Soil moisture
	Soil temperature
	Surface runoff
	Snow depth
	Wind Speed
	Mean NDVI

Land use/cover	Minimum NDVI
	Maximum NDVI
	Standard Deviation NDVI
	Minimum NDTI
	Mean BSI
Soil	Soil texture
	SOC
	Bulk Density
	Nutrients (e.g. N, P, K)
	Contaminants (e.g. As, Hg, Cu, Co)
	Chemical Properties (e.g. pH, CaCO ₃ , CEC)
	Soil Depth
	K Factor
	Wind Erodible Fraction

3. Results

3.1 LPIS/GSAA Data for statistical analysis in EU Olive Orchard Areas

The LPIS/GSA and LUCAS survey statistical overlay process resulted in the selection of 10,405 olive parcels. Considering the 1,033,759 points covering the EU-27 territory, we selected approximately 1% of the LUCAS master points, which are concentrated in seven EU member states with olive groves (Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Slovenia, and Spain). The decision to employ LPIS/GSA data in shapefile format rather than CORINE raster-based data offered various advantages in terms of object-oriented statistical analysis. It also provides accuracy benefits because it allows for more precise definitions of fields and regional patterns. In terms of total olive orchard area in Europe, the CORINE 2018 data totals 47,390 km², while the LPIS/GSA developed by the Soil O-live WP3 totals 41,772 km². Figure 1 compares the two products in Spain and Italy, showing the higher suitability of the LPIS/GSA data.

Figure 1: Visual comparison of olive groves in Spain and Italy using the CORINE and LPIS/GSA datasets.

Figure 2 provides an overview of the spatial distribution of the 10,405 olive parcels included in the Soil O-live Dashboard v1.0. For graphical depiction in the Soil O-live Dashboard v1.0, the information gathered from each LPIS/GSA parcel was pre-processed and averaged at the NUTS3 or hexagon (40 km diameter) level for better illustrating the contents to the user.

Figure 3 depicts some of the vegetation-related environmental variables aggregated by NUTS3 and included into the Soil O-live Dashboard v1.0. These variables combine statistical aggregations of time series of the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalised Difference Tillage Index (NDTI) and Bare Soil Index (BSI) of the sampled parcels from Sentinel-2. Combining these multiple factors reveals the dominant pan-European patterns of vegetation cover due to climatic factors and management practices. For example, the mean NDVI captures the regions where ground cover is more commonly implemented throughout the year, while the minimum, maximum and standard deviation reflect the variation due to climatic factors and management practices. Regions with a lower mean BSI and minimum NDTI are those typically cleared of yellow (senescent) vegetation, leaving bare soil exposed. These variables within the mapping toolbox offer valuable insights into the pan-European context, providing an exploratory resource for interested stakeholders.

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of the 10,405 olive parcels included in the Soil O-live Dashboard v1.0.

Figure 3: Examples of variables aggregated by NUTS3 to provide a pan-mediterranean overview of spatiotemporal vegetation characteristics.

3.2 O-Live Dashboard Interface: Visual Overview

Running the Shiny app in R provides two identical interfaces: an R interface and a web interface. The key distinction is that the web interface is designed to be accessible by end users. It features a sophisticated but user-friendly interface, resembling modern interactive web pages or software. It includes sidebars with dropdown menus, action buttons, interactive maps and plots, and statistical displays.

The online version of the O-live Dashboard v1.0 can be accessed here: https://borrellilab.shinyapps.io/olive_dashboard/. The figures below show some of the functionalities of the O-live Dashboard, which in its current version 1.0 can be divided into two sub-modules to (i) visualize and fully navigate pan-European datasets (Figure 4) and (ii) explore the data structure by performing statistical operations supported by a scatterplot and a boxplot (Figure 5).

A

Interactive Map of Soil-o-live Pilot Sites

Choose Site:
all

Choose Soil Layer:
0-10 cm

Choose Soil Parameter:
Clay

Global Parameters:

Parameters spatially interpolated for LUCAS points in olive-covered areas:
Full Extent

B

Interactive Map of Soil-o-live Pilot Sites

Choose Site:
all

Choose Soil Layer:
0-10 cm

Choose Soil Parameter:
Clay

Global Parameters:
Type of management

Parameters spatially interpolated for LUCAS points in olive-covered areas:
Full Extent

C

Interactive Map of Soil-o-live Pilot Sites

Figure 4: Soil O-live Dashboard sub-module for visualizing and navigating pan-European datasets. Panel a shows an example of data from the 53 Soil O-live project pilot sites. Panel b shows the type of management for each pilot site. Panel c shows an example of data from the 10,405 olive parcels aggregated at the hexagonal unit level.

A

Soil O-LiVe - Data Inventory

B

Soil O-LiVe - Data Inventory

Figure 5: Soil O-live Dashboard sub-module for delving further into the data structure through statistical procedures accompanied by a scatterplot and a boxplot. Panel a depicts the statistical analysis of an entire dataset. Panel b displays the statistical analysis of a specific piece of a dataset.

4. Conclusions

UNIROMA3 collected data, created, and developed the online Soil O-live Dashboard v1.0 to display, navigate, and gain insights from a statistically representative selection of olive groves across Europe, as well as the Soil O-live project's 52 pilot sites. All of the information offered in this report are already integrated in the dashboard and available online. The dashboard will increase in tandem with the Soil O-live project's achievements, housing an increasing amount of data over time. This will apply to both newly created environmental datasets and composite datasets obtained by multivariate statistical studies. Moving forward with the WP3 operations, we intend to expand our research by using the Soil O-live Dashboard to identify key environmental variables that will assist us in parameterizing a dynamic Cover Management factor (C-factor) (Panagos et al., 2015) to be used in computer-based soil erosion simulations, i.e., Deliverable 3.3 of M36 (January 2026). The complete observation and analysis of a massive amount of environmental data provided by the Soil O-live Dashboard will improve our ability to create a better C-factor than the one previously used for pan-European modelling.

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